

Social Media in History Education: Conceptual Foundations and Analytical Frameworks for Teaching and Research

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Abstract: *This essay examines how historical content is presented on social media, drawing on theoretical frameworks and the normative goals of history education. Drawing on current research and clarifying key concepts, it reflects on how digital platforms shape the ways historical knowledge is communicated and perceived. Employing a method of literature-based pedagogical reflection, the study develops a conceptual framework that integrates platform literacy, media literacy, historical literacy, and civic responsibility. This framework offers both theoretical insights and practical guidance for analyzing social media content and designing digitally based history learning strategies, situating them within broader debates on the role of history education in the digital age.*

Note on publication status

This manuscript was prepared with the intention of submission to an international peer-reviewed scholarly journal in the relevant field. Due to contextual circumstances, the publication process for the planned special issue, which had a particular focus on history education and social media, could not be completed, and the paper did not undergo formal peer review.

The present version is therefore made available as a scholarly working paper in order to contribute to ongoing academic discussion.

Citation recommendation

Introduction

Social media now plays a central role in the daily lives of children and adolescents: approximately one-third of global internet users are under 18, and 71 per cent of 15–24-year-olds are online, yet access remains highly uneven across regions and socio-economic contexts.² Beyond communication and entertainment, these platforms serve as spaces for

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This paper is based on the online lecture delivered at the International Conference on Education, History, and Social Studies (ICEHASS) at Universitas Negeri Padang on 15 September 2025, following a gracious invitation extended to the author. In recognition of the hosting university and the substantial advances in Indonesian research on social media and digital learning, this article deliberately draws attention to relevant Indonesian publications.

² Faverio, M., & Sidoti, O. (2024, December 12). *Teens, social media and technology 2024*. Pew Research Center. Retrieved from Stoilova, M., Livingstone, S., & Khazbak, R. (2021). *Investigating risks and opportunities for children in a digital world: A rapid review of the evidence on children's internet use and outcomes* (Innocenti Discussion Paper 2020-03). UNICEF Office of Research – Innocenti, Florence- UNESCO. (2023). *Global education monitoring report 2023: Technology in education — A tool on whose terms?* UNESCO, Paris.

The significance of social media use is also reflected in international debates on the protection of minors, particularly regarding the creation of social media accounts by adolescents under the age of 16. Legally binding prohibitions on account registration for users under 16 have so far been enacted only in Australia, where

informal learning, cultural orientation, and political and historical sense-making, shaping how young people perceive and interpret the world. Although quantitative data on adolescents' deliberate engagement with historical topics on social media remain limited, it is highly likely that platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, and X (formerly Twitter) play a significant role in shaping everyday historical consciousness and collective memory, even when historical content is consumed superficially. For history education, this implies that social media can no longer be regarded as marginal but must be acknowledged as both a significant learning environment and a legitimate object of learning.³

From an analytical perspective, it is useful to distinguish between social media platforms and the user-generated content (UGC) they host. Platforms are defined by their technical architectures, economic models, and algorithmic logics, which shape visibility, circulation, and interaction. UGC, in turn, reflects these platform characteristics through its narrative, visual, and rhetorical features. It should also be acknowledged that user-generated content varies greatly in quality, ranging from rigorously informed and reliable contributions to content marked by historical ignorance or illiteracy. These distinctions enable history education to examine how systemic platform factors and content-specific features jointly affect the presentation, reception, and interpretation of historical knowledge. From this dual perspective, history didactics faces a twofold mandate: to harness the educational potential of social media while critically addressing the epistemic risks of historical content online. The resulting challenge extends beyond classroom practice to teacher education, curriculum design, and educational policy.

Situated at the nexus of history education and social media, this essay explores their interplay by first reviewing the current research landscape and clarifying key concepts and distinctions. It then addresses the specific challenges of engaging with historical content on social platforms. Building on this analysis, the paper proposes a conceptual framework that integrates platform literacy, media literacy, historical literacy, and civic responsibility, offering both theoretical insights and practical guidance. This framework provides a foundation for the analysis of social media content and the development of digitally based history learning strategies, situating them within broader discussions on history education in the digital age.

1. State of the Art: History Education and Social Media

Since the emergence of social media platforms in the early 2000s, international research on history education and social media has grown rapidly, evolving into a nuanced and increasingly interdisciplinary field. Scholars consistently emphasize that these platforms are not merely additional channels for disseminating information about the past; rather, they fundamentally transform the epistemic, cultural, and cognitive conditions under which history and memory is

measures requiring platforms to take reasonable steps to prevent Australians under 16 from having accounts were codified into law and took effect on 10 December 2025. These reforms establish a legal framework aimed at ensuring platform-level compliance and enhancing the protection of underage users. See: eSafety Commissioner. "Social media age restrictions — how they affect under-16s". https://www.esafety.gov.au/young-people/social-media-age-restrictions?utm_source=chatgpt.com.

³ Bennett, W. L. (2008). Changing citizenship in the digital age. In W. L. Bennett (Ed.), *Civic life online: Learning how digital media can engage youth* (pp. 1–24). The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.1162/dmal.9780262524827.001>.

produced, circulated, and appropriated in the public sphere.⁴ User-generated content, shaped by the visibility and distribution logics of social media platforms, today constitutes a key element of global historical culture.

In general, international research in history education consistently agrees that social media holds significant pedagogical potential for history teaching. This goes far beyond the mere richness of primary sources, interpretative commentaries, and educational resources, as professional institutions—including museums, archives, and educational organizations—make them widely accessible with low barriers through social media channels.⁵ Due to their low barriers to entry, digital platforms not only allow user-generated historical content to reach broad audiences but also foster wide participation, enabling marginalized groups and non-institutional actors to share narratives often overlooked in traditional curricula and history textbooks.⁶ Learners can both encounter perspectives and “voices” that might otherwise be rendered invisible and actively participate in historical culture themselves. This engagement can manifest through disseminating results of local oral history projects,⁷ participating in digital commemorative practices, contributing to collaborative knowledge construction, or producing and sharing historical content, such as short-form videos or digital storytelling projects.⁸

Moreover, by engaging with information about the past on social media, students are supported in developing a nuanced understanding of the fundamental epistemic insight that one and the same content can serve multiple functions and contexts. These roles include disseminating verified historical knowledge, documenting local experiences and minority voices, providing educational or entertaining content, facilitating social interaction, contributing to political or societal debates, engaging with memory culture, and, finally, enabling the manipulation or distortion of history.

In addition, through critical engagement with historical content on social media, students can realise that in certain cases, the treatment of the past does not reflect genuine historical inquiry but rather serves as attention-grabbing content, used for recruitment purposes and designed to draw users into the sphere of influence and communication of specific user groups—so-called “echo chambers.”⁹ Extremist organizations, for example, turn historical content into a gateway for ideological indoctrination, strategically exploiting the aesthetic appeal of contemporary social media trends to craft a polished and relatable public

⁴ Carretero, M., Cantabrana, M., & Parellada, C. (Eds.). (2022). *History education in the digital age*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10743-6>. van Dijck, J. (2013). *The culture of connectivity: A critical history of social media*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press. van Dijck, J., Poell, T., & de Waal, M. (2018). *The Platform Society: Public Values in a Connective World*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press. Hoskins, A. (Ed.). (2018). *Digital memory studies: Media pasts in transition*. New York, NY: Routledge. Singh, L., & Ahmad, T. A. (2022). Examining the impact of social media on youth and its future for history learning. *Paramita: Historical Studies Journal*, 32(2), 253–262. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15294/paramita.v32i2.35055>.

⁵ Cf. Widiadi, A. N., Sheehan, M., & Shep, S. (2022). The potential of web-based historical sources as learning resources to foster students' historical thinking skills. *Paramita: Historical Studies Journal*, 32(1), 138–148. <https://doi.org/10.15294/paramita.v32i1.31048>

⁶ Cf. Kansteiner, W. (2017). *History and memory in the digital age*. New York, NY: Routledge.

⁷ See, e.g., Jamiludin, J., & Darnawati, D. (2022). *Project-Based Digital Photovoice: Teaching local history through the visual method*. *Social and Education History*, 11(3), 245–274. <https://doi.org/10.17583/hse.10444>. Hood, C., & Reid, P. H. (2018). *Social media as a vehicle for user engagement with local history: A case study in the North East of Scotland*. *Journal of Documentation*, 74(4), 741–762. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-12-2017-0167>.

⁸ Widiadi, A. N., Sheehan, M., & Shep, S. (2022). The potential of web-based historical sources as learning resources to foster students' historical thinking skills. *Paramita: Historical Studies Journal*, 32(1), 138–148. <https://doi.org/10.15294/paramita.v32i1.31048>

⁹ Pariser, E. (2011). *The filter bubble: What the internet is hiding from you*. New York, NY: Penguin.

persona. Research on digital environments has demonstrated that there is a significant risk for the online radicalization of vulnerable adolescents.¹⁰

Against this backdrop, critically engaging with historical content on social media can enable students not only to gain epistemic insight into the constructed nature of history and collective memory, but also to critically examine the diverse ways in which historical content is used and misused on attention-driven platforms. The need for such evaluative competencies arises directly from the underlying architectural logic of social media, centered on the collection and monetization of user data, a practice often characterized as platform capitalism.¹¹ Platforms incentivize high levels of interaction—such as likes, comments, and prolonged dwell time—because increased engagement promotes identity signaling, allowing companies to refine user profiles for targeted advertising and other revenue-generating purposes. In this environment, historical narratives are not presented randomly; instead, algorithmic architectures filter and distribute content based on engagement metrics to maximize data production.¹²

Consequently, international research in history education highlights that engagement with the past on social media is governed less by truth-oriented validation and more by attention-driven logics, inherently prioritizing virality, emotional resonance, and attention-grabbing content at the expense of reasoned, nuanced, evidence-based, and multiperspective interpretations. As a result, brief, simplified, and often one-sided representations that are visually striking, fragmented, and decontextualized—and frequently imbued with emotion or sensationalism—tend to be preferred over rigorous historiographical analysis and deliberate, standards-oriented engagement.¹³ This shift is particularly critical as the benefit of low-barrier participation in user-generated content coincides with the erosion of subject-oriented and discursive quality control. Without the traditional editorial gatekeeping of professional institutions, the authority of a claim is decoupled from its evidentiary basis, leaving learners to navigate a challenging “post-truth” social media landscape.¹⁴

This issue presents multiple difficulties for students, who generally lack the robust historical knowledge needed to rapidly and effectively assess historical content encountered on social media. The knowledge gap hypothesis from mass communication research suggests that, as the flow of media information increases, individuals with higher levels of education and structured subject knowledge are better equipped to assess, interpret, and contextualize information, while those with less background knowledge are more likely to accept

¹⁰ E.g., Croci, G. (2024). Online Radicalization and Ways to Counteract its Impact. Social Justice Center. Tbilisi, Georgia. https://socialjustice.org.ge/uploads/products/pdf/Online_radicalization_1708431060.pdf.

¹¹ Srnicek, N. (2017). *Platform Capitalism*. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press. Gillespie, T. (2018). *Custodians of the Internet: Platforms, Content Moderation, and the Hidden Decisions That Shape Social Media*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.

¹² van Dijck, J. (2013). *The Culture of Connectivity: A Critical History of Social Media*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press. Gillespie, T. (2018). *Custodians of the Internet: Platforms, Content Moderation, and the Hidden Decisions that Shape Social Media*. Yale University Press.

¹³ Haydn, T. (2017). The impact of social media on history education: A view from England. *Yesterday & Today*, (17), 23–45. doi:10.17159/2223-0386/2017/n17a2. Haydn, T., & Ribbens, K. (2017). Social media, new technologies and history education. In M. Carretero, S. Berger, & M. Grever (Eds.), *Palgrave Handbook of Research in Historical Culture and Education* (pp. 735–753). London, UK: Palgrave Macmillan. doi:10.1057/978-1-137-52908-4_3. Eichhorn, K. (2022). *Content*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

¹⁴ Journell, W. (2021). *Post-truth rhetoric and today's social studies: Strategies for equipping civic-minded learners*. New York, NY: Teachers College Press. Lazio, L. K. (2023). Preventing belief in misinformation: Current and future directions for the field. *Journal of Applied Research in Memory and Cognition*, 12(3), 307–309. <https://doi.org/10.1037/mac000136>

information uncritically.¹⁵ From the learners' perspective, empirical research shows that users who rely mainly on social media for historical information tend to exhibit lower levels of cognitive elaboration and structured knowledge acquisition compared with those in traditional learning environments. This pattern, which can be understood as a vicious circle, persists unless cognitive elaboration is deliberately promoted.¹⁶

Evidence also indicates that learners—and the broader public—often struggle to assess the plausibility and evidential basis of historical and to contextualize individual pieces of content meaningfully. They often have limited familiarity with reliable analytical and methodological tools, as well as with trustworthy reference points and institutional sources that could serve as a foundation for critical orientation and fact-checking. Research further shows that many students rely excessively on superficial cues such as likes, shares, follower counts, or the aesthetic appeal of content rather than on substantive evidence.¹⁷ Conversely, some students develop a generalized skepticism or distrust toward all historical information on social media, feeling unable to evaluate it critically.¹⁸

In addition, research suggests that exposure to diverse perspectives does not automatically promote critical engagement, and students frequently struggle to integrate fragmented and decontextualized historical claims into a coherent narrative or understanding. Emotional and affective responses often guide their judgments, complicating the detection of bias, distortion, or ideological slants. Frequent exposure to misinformation in so-called “filter bubbles” exacerbates these challenges. Without strategic pedagogical training, learners risk encountering both individually targeted and historically unprecedented volumes of false or misleading information, for which they are often ill-equipped, while engaging only superficially with historical content and thereby hindering the development of reflective historical thinking.¹⁹

Drawing on his empirical work,²⁰ Sam Wineburg—arguably the most internationally recognized scholar on the challenges of historical reasoning in digital environments—offers valuable guidelines for history teaching. He assumes that historical thinking—including

¹⁵ Büchi, M. (2017). Digital inequalities: differentiated internet use and social implications. (Dissertation, University of Zurich) <https://doi.org/10.5167/uzh-148989>.

¹⁶ Frauhammer, L. T., & Dreston, J. H. (2025). *How cognitive elaboration fosters knowledge acquisition on social media—a field experiment*. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 30(5), zmaf014. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcmc/zmaf014>.

¹⁷ Carretero, M., Rodriguez-Moneo, M., Cantabrana, M., & Parellada, C. (2022). *History education in the digital age*. In M. Carretero, M. Cantabrana, & C. Parellada (Eds.), *History education in the digital age* (pp. 3–21). Springer. Haydn, T., & Ribbens, K. (2017). Social media, new technologies and history education. In M. Carretero, S. Berger, & M. Grever (Eds.), *Palgrave Handbook of Research in Historical Culture and Education* (pp. 735–753). London, UK: Palgrave Macmillan. doi:10.1057/978-1-137-52908-4_3. Eichhorn, K. (2022). *Content*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

Wineburg, S., McGrew, S., Breakstone, J., & Ortega, T. (2016). Evaluating information: The cornerstone of civic online reasoning. Stanford, CA: Stanford History Education Group. Retrieved from <https://stacks.stanford.edu/file/druid:fv751yt5934/SHEG%20Evaluating%20Information%20Online.pdf>.

¹⁸ Toledo, W. (2021). “I just saw it on Facebook, so that isn’t true”: How the omnipresence of social media complicates history education. In J. P. Carpenter & K. C. Barton (Eds.), *Teaching social studies with social media* (pp. 95–112). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-64802-657-720251009>

¹⁹ McGrew, S., Breakstone, J., Ortega, T., Smith, M., & Wineburg, S. (2018). *Can students evaluate online sources? Learning from assessments of civic online reasoning*. *Theory & Research in Social Education*, 46(2), 165–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00933104.2017.1416320>

²⁰ Wineburg, S. (2018). *Why learn history (when it’s already on your phone)*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press. McGrew, S., Breakstone, J., Ortega, T., Smith, M., & Wineburg, S. (2020). *Learning to evaluate: An intervention in civic online reasoning*. *Computers & Education*, 145, Article 103711. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103711>.

sourcing, corroboration, contextualization, and perspective-taking—is cognitively demanding and not intuitive,²¹ and therefore requires targeted instruction, a need made even more pressing by the uncontrolled circulation of large volumes of easily accessible non-professional user-generated content.

Wineburg’s approach emphasizes basic strategies that support learners in critically evaluating online historical content. A central principle is “lateral reading,”²² which directs students to consult multiple sources across different platforms before returning to the original content and to decide whether to engage with or ignore it—a process referred to as “critical ignoring” by Wineburg. For example, if a student encounters a historical claim on social media, they might verify it through a so-called “quick check” on Wikipedia or a recognized website (online encyclopedia, museum, archive). This process trains learners to step beyond the immediate platform, actively comparing information rather than taking it at face value, and to slow down, resisting the impulse to click, like, share, or react. In doing so, it fosters mental distance from superficial cues—such as thumbnails, headlines, and social signals—that often trigger impulsive engagement.

Believing that the analysis of online sources is essential both for modern historical scholarship and for fostering digitally literate, responsible citizens, Wineburg and his colleagues have developed the Civic Online Reasoning (COR) framework,²³ which can be easily applied in history lessons. Designed to support students in analyzing historical content online, it centers on three core questions that should consistently guide their production and consumption of digital material: (a) Who is behind the information? (b) What evidence supports the claims? (c) How do other sources corroborate or challenge the information? This COR framework aligns in key aspects with the Indonesian concept of “deep thinking”²⁴ and is generally highly adaptable for international history education.

Complementing these approaches, Wineburg strongly emphasizes digital literacy²⁵ in history education, aiming to equip students with the skills to understand how internet platforms function and vary, and how media formats influence narratives, emphasize particular perspectives.²⁶

²¹ Wineburg, S. (2001). *Historical thinking and other unnatural acts: Charting the future of teaching the past*. Philadelphia, PA: Temple University Press.

²² Wineburg, S., & McGrew, S. (2019). *Lateral reading: Reading less and learning more when evaluating digital information*. Stanford, CA: Stanford History Education Group. Breakstone, J., Smith, M., & Wineburg, S. (2021). Beyond verification: Lateral reading and students’ ability to evaluate online information. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 52(3), 1184–1199. doi:10.1111/bjet.13105.

²³ Wineburg, S., Breakstone, J., Smith, M., McGrew, S., & Ortega, T. (2020). *Civic Online Reasoning: Curriculum evaluation*. Stanford University Digital Repository. Retrieved from https://cor.inquirygroup.org/research/cor-curriculum-evaluation/?utm_source=chatgpt.com. Breakstone, J., Smith, M., Wineburg, S., Rapaport, A., Carle, J., Garland, M., & Saavedra, A. (2021). *Students’ Civic Online Reasoning: A National Portrait*. Stanford Graduate School of Education Open Archive. Retrieved from https://openarchive.stanford.edu/node/2597?utm_source=chatgpt.com. McGrew, S., Breakstone, J., & Smith, M. (2023). *Civic Online Reasoning Across the Curriculum: Developing and Testing the Efficacy of Digital Literacy Lessons*. *Educational Research Journal/SAGE*. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/23328584231176451>.

²⁴ Cf. Basri, I., Fatimah, S., & Hastuti, H. (2024). *Learning history with DeepThink: A model to train critical thinking skills in history education*. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 16(2), 1041–1051.

²⁵ See for example: Denbo, S. (2016, September 1). Digital literacy. *Perspectives on History*. American Historical Association. Retrieved from <https://www.historians.org/publications-and-directories/perspectives-on-history/september-2016/digital-literacy>.

²⁶ Caulfield, M., & Wineburg, S. (2023). *Verified: How to think straight, get duped less, and make better decisions about what to believe online*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.

In conclusion, the growing body of research on history education and social media converges on the idea that history education should focus on equipping students with a triple-pillar competency framework encompassing platform literacy, media literacy, and historical literacy.²⁷

Platform literacy enables students to understand how the technical and economic architecture of social media—including engagement-driven algorithms and visibility biases—determines which historical content is amplified or marginalized. These effects arise primarily from the platform’s structural design rather than the content itself, meaning that algorithmic mechanisms dictate visibility to specific audiences. Media literacy enables learners to critically examine the ways in which user-generated formats—including short videos, memes, threads, image macros, stories, reels, TikTok challenges, educational videos, and infographics—influence the construction and communication of historical knowledge. *Historical literacy* remains the essential foundation, enabling students to apply rigorous historical thinking to assess the plausibility and evidentiary support of narratives or claims about the past. Its significance continues to grow in a digital age where historical knowledge is “always on the phone” (Wineburg, 2018) but rarely verified.

2. Differentiating Platforms and Content Types on Social Media

For effective history education about and with historical content on social media, it is essential to distinguish both between different platform architectures and between different formats within social media platforms. At the structural level, a fundamental distinction must be drawn between information-oriented platforms, such as Wikipedia, recommended by Wineburg²⁸ for “quick check”, and attention-driven social media platforms like TikTok, Instagram, or YouTube.

In contrast to social media platforms, which prioritize visibility, engagement, and algorithmic circulation—as emphasized by Wineburg—reputable information platforms operate according to epistemic logics grounded in verifiability, source transparency, and editorial oversight. Wikipedia occupies a central position in history education: as a collaboratively maintained, non-profit platform with formal editorial guidelines, it emphasizes neutrality, transparency, and verifiability. While critical engagement remains necessary—since inaccuracies or biases can still occur—such shortcomings typically stem from human oversight or editorial limitations rather than from the systematic amplification of popularity and engagement that characterizes social media, where substantive content curation often plays a marginal role.

Within social media, historical content appears in a wide variety of formats, each with distinct credibility profiles and pedagogical potential. Short videos, for example, are highly engaging and can quickly attract learners’ attention, and professionally produced content by

²⁷ This overview concentrates on overarching research trends in history education and social media. For reasons of space and scope, many insightful studies addressing specific platforms (e.g., TikTok), media formats (e.g., memes, explainer videos), historical skills (e.g., historical judgment), or general digital tools are not included. Instead, attention is drawn to a few illustrative studies in these fields. See, e.g., Banerjee, D. (2024). The impact of digital tools on the teaching of history: A comparative study of traditional and technology-integrated teaching methods. *International Journal for interdisciplinary Research*, 6(3), 1–5. Irmansyah, H., & Atmaja, T. S. (2025). Transformation of history learning methods in the digital era: Challenges and opportunities in schools. *Indonesian Journal of Educational Development (IJED)*, 6(1), 264–277. Lee, B. N. (2022). Media for history learning in the digital era. *SPEKTA: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat: Teknologi dan Aplikasi*, 3(2), 117–128. Retrieved from <http://journal2.uad.ac.id/index.php/spekta>.

²⁸ Caulfield, M., & Wineburg, S. (2024, January 24). *Teaching students how to use Wikipedia as a tool for research*. Edutopia. Retrieved December 31, 2025, from <https://www.edutopia.org/article/using-wikipedia-for-research>.

institutions with public responsibility—such as academic organizations—is typically accurate,²⁹ well-sourced, and suitable for classroom use, whereas user-generated videos may oversimplify or distort complex events, requiring critical guidance. Images and infographics similarly range from reliable, carefully curated archival photographs and museum visuals to questionable examples that, upon verification using reverse image search tools, prove to be inaccurate or misleading.

Text-based content, including social media threads, blog posts, and educational summaries, also follows a spectrum of credibility. High-credibility texts are produced by experts or academic institutions, feature accurate citations, and rely on trustworthy references, while medium-level texts, such as popular journalism or educational blogs, may offer less rigorous verification, and opinion-based or hobbyist content varies in reliability. Livestreams and vlogs can immerse learners in historical contexts, again with credibility highest when led by experts or public institutions, and lower when entertainment is prioritized over factual accuracy or educational responsibility. Memes and humorous media are particularly engaging for learners, yet their content must be critically evaluated, and their ironic rhetoric—including symbols, allegories, and metaphors—rigorously analyzed. Their widespread appeal makes them effective tools for exploring narrative framing, emotional persuasion, and misinformation, as well as for fostering students' own creative productions.³⁰

Digital reenactments and first-person narratives form a distinct content type, allowing learners to experience historical events from an individual perspective, fostering empathy and historical perspective-taking. Their instructional value is highest when produced by institutions with public responsibility according to professional standards, including transparent delineation between factual sources and dramatized interpretation, fact-based research, didactic clarity, narrative consistency, and clear "making-of" explanations that show how sources and creative interpretation are combined. Comparing best-practice examples with less reliable or amateur content helps learners become sensitive to the many ways in which formats can blur the boundaries between fact and fiction.

By focusing on professionally produced content by professional institutions with public responsibility—including short videos, podcasts, infographics, archival images, museum-led livestreams, and digital reenactments—students and teachers gain access not only to reliable sources and educational resources, as well as a variety of everyday opportunities to engage in critical thinking, but also to exemplary models of high-quality engagement. Analyzing these contributions shows students how historical content can be accurately researched, contextualized, and creatively communicated, inspiring their own interpretive or creative projects.

3. Excursus: AI in Social Media: Implications for History Education

In contemporary social media, AI has already begun to shape the historical content students encounter, and its impact is expected to grow substantially in the years ahead, shaping both

²⁹ See, for example, a critical commentary on a highly popular German explainer video channel operated by public-service broadcasters: Popp, S., & Röder, D. (2022). Why history education? Exploring YouTube explanatory videos – The German example of *Mr Wissen2go Geschichte*. *International Journal of Research on History Didactics, History Education and History Culture (JHEC)*, 43, 141–155. Retrieved from https://jhec.wochenschau-verlag.de/wp-content/uploads/sites/23/2024/01/issue_2022.pdf#page=142

³⁰ Cf. Persada, S. S., Sariyatun, & Musadad, A. A. (2023). *Trends in the use of digital media integrated with primary sources as teaching materials for high school history subjects in Indonesia*. *International Journal of Research in Education Humanities and Commerce*, 4(3). <https://doi.org/10.37602/IJREHC.2023.4315>.

what learners see and how they interpret it.³¹ This field presents a central challenge for history education in the context of online platforms and beyond,³² and experts agree that, looking ahead, AI platforms specifically curated for educational purposes need to be developed and implemented in educational environments. To date, this project, as well as international educational research on AI in history education, remains at an early stage. The following discussion therefore offers only a brief overview and does not claim to be exhaustive. Nevertheless, addressing AI is essential when engaging with social media in history education.

While many AI-related challenges in the history classroom overlap with general social media issues—such as algorithmic curation, popularity-driven visibility, and user-generated misinformation—AI introduces additional complexities. AI-driven systems not only rank and recommend content based on user data and interactions but can also generate texts, images, videos, memes, that appear authentic yet may include subtle errors, misattributed quotes, or entirely fabricated events or simulated historical sources and personas. Deepfakes or AI-generated historical influencers, including bot accounts, can mimic authenticity and emotional engagement. For instance, they can depict historical figures performing actions or delivering speeches that never occurred.³³ Beyond the issue of deepfakes, typical AI-related errors when engaging with historical content include invented quotes, fabricated or misattributed sources (“hallucinated authority”), slight alterations of dates, anachronistic reasoning (e.g., projecting contemporary norms onto past contexts), and oversimplified historical narratives.³⁴

From the perspective of history education, learners must be explicitly guided to recognize these pitfalls. A first practical classroom approach could be the critical annotation of AI-assisted historical content with typical mistakes. Students receive a carefully selected, AI-generated brief historical profile of a person or event, provided by the teacher, and systematically annotate it by comparing it with textbooks, reliable online encyclopedias, and peer-reviewed sources in order to identify factual errors, unsupported claims, and narrative biases. In doing so, they distinguish between correct and incorrect statements, as well as between claims corroborated by sources and those that reflect AI-generated interpretation.

³¹ Ouida, H., Marfouk, M., El Gourari, W., & Ed-Dali, R. (2025). *History education and generative AI: Navigating accuracy and bias*. *Etudes Langue et Littérature*, (3), 119–137. Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning*. Boston: Center for Curriculum Redesign. Milan, S. (2020). Artificial intelligence, social media, and digital media literacy. *Journal of Digital Social Research*, 2(1), 1–25. Milan, S. (2020). Artificial intelligence, social media, and digital media literacy. *Journal of Digital Social Research*, 2(1), 1–25.

³² See, e.g., Carretero, M., & Gartner, E. (2024). Artificial intelligence and historical thinking: A dialogic exploration of ChatGPT/Inteligencia artificial y pensamiento histórico: Una exploración dialógica del ChatGPT. *Estudios de Psicología*, 45(1), 80–102. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02109395241241379>. American Historical Association. (2025). *Guiding principles for artificial intelligence in history education*. Washington, DC: Author. Retrieved from <https://www.historians.org/resource/guiding-principles-for-artificial-intelligence-in-history-education/>.

³³ Vaccari, C., & Chadwick, A. (2020). Deepfakes and disinformation: Exploring the liberty to deceive and the right to know. *Social Theory and Practice*, 46(1), 205–215. <https://doi.org/10.5840/soctheorpract202021192>

³⁴ See, e.g., Kelly, S. M. (2023). ChatGPT and the ghost of historians past. *The American Historical Review*, 128(2), 523–530. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/rhad214>. Mills, D. (2023, June). Generative AI and the future of history. *History Today*, 73(6). Retrieved from <https://www.historytoday.com>. See e.g., Gulickson, A., & Spahr, S. (2024). Hallucinations in the archive: Large language models and historical research. *Digital Humanities Quarterly*, 18(1). <http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/18/1/000729/000729.html>

Herbold, S., Hautli-Janisz, A., Heuer, U., Kikteva, Z., & Trautsch, A. (2023). A large-scale comparison of human-written versus ChatGPT-generated essays. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), Article 18617.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-45644-9>

Kelly, S. M. (2023). ChatGPT and the ghost of historians past. *The American Historical Review*, 128(2), 523–530. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/rhad214>

Verification of images or videos should also be carried out using tools like Google Reverse Image.

Despite these risks, some scholars emphasize that AI-generated content also offers pedagogical potential when used with care. For example, students can explore multiple perspectives, simulate historical scenarios, create alternative histories, and engage creatively with historical narratives. However, such activities require clear guidance from the teacher and careful verification of the outcomes against reliable historical sources, ensuring that creative or exploratory exercises remain grounded in factual accuracy and critical historical thinking.

4. Analytical Framework for Engaging with Historical Content on Social Media

The following section outlines some key considerations for classroom engagement with historical content on social media. The first subsection identifies the core analytical domains required for a systematic analysis of social media–based historical content. The focus is placed on some exemplary practices for classroom implementation; however, a degree of repetition in the already explained definitional area is unavoidable. The second subsection operationalizes these analytical domains into guiding questions primarily intended for teachers, which may also be adapted as a scaffolded analytical framework for students. The emphasis is deliberately on foundational rather than detailed questions, since concrete implementation necessarily varies according to topic, instructional goals, and learners’ prior knowledge and cognitive capacities and critically engaging with social media content in the history classroom. The section concludes with brief remarks on risk preparedness when using, critically engaging with, and producing historical content on social media platforms.

5.1 Analytical domains

Platform literacy is a key didactic field that helps students understand how social media platforms structure, visibility, attention, and engagement, as well as the mode of encountering history. Unlike traditional media analysis, the focus is not on verifying the factual accuracy of historical content, but on uncovering the underlying logics governing platform architecture: These include largely unmoderated user-generated content, engagement- and virality-driven algorithms, interface features, recommendation systems, and platform-specific elements such as Stories, Reels, hashtags, and trending feeds. Taken together, these mechanisms determine which media types are amplified, which historical content is highlighted in relation to them, and which audiences are most likely to encounter it.

To make these abstract structures tangible, students benefit from both direct instruction on core mechanisms—such as algorithmic selection, the attention economy, and technical affordances—and activity-based exercises that allow them to observe these processes in practice. One such exercise is “My Bubble – Your Bubble”, which targets algorithmic awareness. Students begin by comparing results from an identical historical prompt (e.g., The Java War 1825–1830) and reflect on why different users encounter different content. This exercise reveals how algorithmic pre-filtering shapes what users see and highlights the personalized nature of digital feeds. As an extension, students can work in small groups on recommendation algorithm mapping, following recommendation paths on platforms such as YouTube, TikTok, or Instagram for the same historical topic. Within these groups, they compare their findings, noting patterns in which content is suggested, how posts are amplified, and how users are guided into particular “filter bubbles.” This hands-on approach helps students realize how platform algorithms determine content prioritization.

A complementary exercise could examine how the highest-ranked posts on a historical topic appear across multiple platforms. Working in groups, students gather data from a specific point in time across Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, and Twitter, observing which posts appear first and considering how platform features—such as hashtags, trending feeds, recommendation algorithms, and interface layout—affect visibility. The exercise underscores how the same historical content is filtered, ranked, and presented differently across platforms. By sidestepping the issue of factual accuracy, it renders the mechanics of algorithms and their influence on historical sense-making tangible.

These exercises can be adapted to different grade levels. Younger students may focus on simple observation and classification, while older students can engage in detailed comparisons, track patterns across platforms, and reflect on the underlying structures that shape what historical content reaches audiences.

The second essential analytical domain is *media literacy*, understood as a distinct area separate from both platform literacy and historical source criticism. While platform literacy focuses on the functional and structural features of digital platforms, media literacy examines how social media content genres and types shape historical representation and meaning. Although the boundaries between media and platform literacy can sometimes blur, media literacy primarily addresses how historical messages are constructed within media formats, rather than how platforms organize or distribute content.

Media analysis applies across all forms of digital and analogue historical representation, but in the context of social media, typical tendencies such as brevity, simplicity, deliberate subjectivity, multimodality, visual–audio framing, fragmentation, decontextualization, and emotionalization strongly influence how content is perceived, often before any source-critical or contextual evaluation. Students can experience this in a practical exercise: working in small groups, they simulate posting strategies aimed at maximizing visibility on different platforms. Focusing on a specific curricular topic, they create drafts of posts tailored to Instagram, TikTok, and Twitter, experimenting with platform-specific formats. On Instagram, they design visually striking posts with images or infographics, balancing visual appeal with limited space for historical explanation. On TikTok, they produce short videos highlighting key events or narratives, navigating the constraints of simplification and dramatization. On Twitter, they draft concise threads, compressing complex information within strict character limits. During the reflection phase, students discuss the challenges of reconciling the pursuit of maximum visibility (reach) with the rigors of historical complexity and evidence. This includes a critical look at how social media formats often discourage the use of formal references and the nuanced presentation of primary and secondary source material.

The third analytical domain, historical literacy, approaches social media posts as either primary or secondary sources, assessing claims differently depending on their type: secondary narratives are evaluated for accuracy and contextualization, while primary sources are examined for authenticity and situational context. Media literacy examines how historical meaning is conveyed through media types. Historical literacy, in contrast, analyzes what is said about the past, by whom, to whom, and with what intention, assessing the evidence supporting individual claims and the extent to which overall narratives are multi-perspective, historically accurate, and aligned with the creator’s intentions. Although this domain will be explored in greater detail in the presentation of the analytical framework below (5.2), it is important to highlight a relevant practical aspect: many students engage with historical content on social media not only as an object of critical analysis, but also as a resource for acquiring historical knowledge, often for school purposes. Since unprofessional social media

content is mainly ill-suited for structured knowledge acquisition, a proven strategy to address this in history education is the periodic implementation of the flipped classroom mode.³⁵ Students prepare a historical topic at home using a combination of social media materials, textbook excerpts, and other reliable sources, guided by targeted questions. Classroom time is then devoted to in-depth discussion and evaluation of the content, along with elaborated reflection on the characteristics, strengths, and limitations of the social media sources. By carefully selecting materials, teachers help students recognize the inherent limitations of social media content and reinforce the importance of consulting additional sources when acquiring historical knowledge through digital media.

A fourth essential analytical domain is *analysis through practical doing*, which builds on and intersects with the previously discussed domains.³⁶ Active media production is widely recognized as a cornerstone of media education and is considered not merely a teaching method but a distinct competency in its own right. From the perspective of history education, learners develop both historical and media literacy by deepening subject knowledge while actively engaging with the communication of history in digital contexts.

Practical activities in this domain include creating historically grounded Instagram profiles of historical figures or events, producing short educational TikToks or Reels that condense complex historical knowledge, or conducting collaborative thread-based debates simulating historical controversies and multiple perspectives. These exercises make historical learning processes explicit: students research and verify information, present evidence transparently, consider multiple perspectives, and reflect on how rhetoric, narrative structure, and visual design adapt to platform conventions and shape historical content.

While extended production projects may require more time or cross-curricular collaboration, autonomous content creation can also be implemented in short, low-threshold tasks using existing platform mechanics. These tasks do not require advanced technical skills and can be carried out individually or collaboratively within brief instructional units. Examples include creating counter-narrative posts in response to misleading or one-sided historical representations on social media,³⁷ producing historical memes, infographics, or concise video summaries, and collaboratively writing short posts from the perspective of historical actors or everyday people—explicitly distinguishing between source-based content and imaginative

³⁵ See, e.g., van Alten, D. C. D. (2021). *Flipped learning in secondary education history classrooms: What are the effects and what is the role of self-regulated learning?* (Doctoral dissertation, Utrecht University). Utrecht University Repository. Online: https://dspace.library.uu.nl/handle/1874/401414?utm_source=chatgpt.com
Fadli, M. R., Rochmat, S., Sudrajat, A., Aman, A., Rohman, A., & Kuswono, K. (2022). *Flipped classroom in history learning to improve students' critical thinking*. International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE), 11(3), 1416–1423. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v11i3.22785>. Sulastrri, S., Sucipto, S., Purnamasari, H., & Suciati, S. (2025). *The flipped classroom with educational TikTok improves students' understanding of local history: Model kelas terbalik dengan TikTok pendidikan meningkatkan pemahaman siswa tentang sejarah lokal*. Indonesian Journal of Innovation Studies, 26(4), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.21070/ijins.v26i4.1602>.

³⁶ See, e.g., Boggs, J. A. (2022). *Recording the skills of interpreting the past: A case study on historical thinking skills developed through student-generated video* (Doctoral dissertation, Liberty University). Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/doctoral/3716>. Lee, N. J., & Carpenter, J. P. (2015). Creative and participatory history: Students as social media creators. *The Social Studies*, 106(3), 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00377996.2015.1023715>. Northeastern University. (2024). *Activating engagement and cognition with student-generated historical images and artifacts*. Center for Advancing Teaching and Learning. Retrieved from <https://academic-innovation.northeastern.edu/activating-engagement-and-cognition-with-student-generated-historical-images-and-artifacts/>

³⁷ Hodgin, E., & Kahne, J. (2018). Misinformation in the social studies classroom: What is the role of distributive justice? *Social Education*, 82(4), 208–212.

reconstruction. Across all examples, the focus lies not only on the final product but on justifying production choices with respect to historical quality.³⁸

5.2 Source Analysis 2.0: A Concise Framework for Evaluating Historical Content on Social Media

This section offers an adaptable guideline for teachers—and, where appropriate, for students—to engage critically with historical content on social media, deliberately focused on the essential aspects of analysis. Its foundation is Source Analysis 2.0, a didactic concept that, while not yet firmly established internationally, extends traditional source criticism to the digital environment by integrating platform, media, historical, and civic literacy, while also addressing AI-generated and AI-assisted content.

The following sequence of analytical steps begins with a platform analysis, exploring the social media environment. It then moves to an examination of the historical content itself, approached as either a primary or secondary source depending on the learning objectives. This is followed by media analysis, which considers the interplay between the platform, the historical content and its media framing and presentation, and concludes with reflections on civic responsibility, with the option to include redesign or other creative tasks.

This sequence, however, is not prescriptive: depending on the instructional focus and objectives, the steps may be reordered, or individual elements may be emphasized independently. What is crucial is that learners develop a clear and coherent understanding of the analytical dimensions, including civic responsibility, that they must consider when engaging with historical content online—particularly on social media platforms.

Platform Literacy: When analyzing historical content on social media, it is pedagogically sound to begin by directing attention to the platform itself. Which platform published the content—X/Twitter, TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, or another? What are the characteristic media types of this platform—for example, text posts, memes, videos, or livestreams—and what opportunities and constraints do these formats present for the presentation of historical content? What are my own experiences with this platform in relation to history? How are strategies such as hashtags, trends, or challenges employed to capture attention and enhance virality? Further, algorithmic awareness is crucial: why am I seeing this content and these recommendations? By examining user interactions—particularly comments, likes, shares, and other forms of engagement—students can gain valuable insights into audience reception and emerging discourses. They can also reflect on patterns of participation, asking who is actively contributing to the conversation and whose voices are possibly absent or marginalized, as far as this can be identified.

Authorship and Audience: Understanding authorship and audience is fundamental to all forms of source criticism, including media analysis and fact-checking practices; it is therefore treated here as a distinct analytical dimension. Key guiding questions include: Who created this content, and what is the creator’s background, expertise, or institutional affiliation? How can this information be identified or verified? Is the content produced by an individual, a collective, an institution, or an anonymous account, and what does this imply for accountability and reliability? Does the authors position themselves as a historian, eyewitness,

³⁸ For AI-assisted or -generated content see, e.g., Open University. (2025). *Critical AI literacy framework*. Open University. <https://www.open.ac.uk/research/critical-ai-literacy>. Long, D., & Magerko, B. (2020). What is AI literacy? Competencies and design considerations. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1–16). New York, NY: ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376727>.

educator, activist, entertainer, or influencer, and how should this role be taken into account during analysis?

Who is the intended audience, and which indicators—such as language, tone, references, platform choice, or visual style—signal this audience? Who might benefit from this representation of the past, and whose interests might it serve? Does the content address a local, national, or global public, and how are historical references adapted to that audience’s assumed prior knowledge? Finally, learners should consider whether there are signs that artificial intelligence was involved in the creation of the content, and if so, whether and how this can be determined.³⁹

Historical Content Analysis and Source Criticism: Shifting the focus to the historical content itself, the analysis is guided by a set of well-established essential questions. What is the exact historical topic, what prior knowledge do students bring, and where does this knowledge come from? When was the post published, and is there a connection to a current social or political issue? What are the main claims, and what narrative messages are being conveyed? Are references or sources provided to support these claims? How reliable are the sources, and what evidence supports them? Is the style argumentative and evidence-based, or rather general, assertive, or persuasive in nature? What is the main purpose of the post—does it aim to inform, entertain, educate, persuade, raise awareness, engage in political agitation or advocacy, provoke discussion, polarize audiences, incite hatred, or mock people and events? Which indicators in the content or presentation suggest this purpose?

Regarding fact-checking and narrative evaluation, students are held to lateral reading, verifying claims across textbooks, educational or knowledge platforms (such as Wikipedia and other online encyclopedias). This may include using reverse image searches to check the origin and authenticity of visual content. Students then assess: Are the claims accurate, partially true, or false? Related to narrative analysis, key questions include to what extent storytelling, dramatization, or the emphasis on particular perspectives shape the content, whether multiple perspectives are presented, and whose voices may be missing.

It is particularly important that students become familiar with reliable reference points and fact-checking tools. Examples include: websites of professional institutions with public responsibility, such as government agencies, national archives, museums, and research institutes; fact-checking tools like Google Fact Check Explorer, which searches verified fact-checking databases worldwide (e.g., AFP, Snopes, BBC) for contemporary historical topics or myths, Wayback Machine (Archive.org), which shows older versions of websites, Wikipedia Talk Pages and Version History, allowing students to examine who edited an article, when, and which points were discussed; and Google Scholar, which helps verify secondary sources and can provide information about authors’ scholarly backgrounds or institutional affiliations.

Media Literacy: To evaluate how digital formats and design shape the presentation of history on social media, Source Analysis 2.0 requires a structured examination of media features, which, while overlapping with content and platform analysis, maintains its own distinct focus. The inquiry begins with immediate perception: which design elements—such as headline styling, high-contrast colors, rapid movement, or bold text overlays—capture attention, create a “thumb-stop” effect, and guide the viewer’s gaze through an implicit hierarchy of importance? From a semiotic perspective, how do choices of typeface, the balance between text and images, and audiovisual elements such as music, sound effects, and voiceovers shape attention, convey historical messages, and evoke emotional responses?

³⁹ Tools such as OpenAI Text Classifier and GPTZero can help estimate whether a text was likely AI-generated. They analyze textual patterns to provide probabilistic indications, but their results are not fully reliable.

Furthermore, how does the stylization of historical content influence visibility, audience engagement, and the ways in which the content is shaped and perceived? Are there any aesthetic markers that could indicate AI-generated imagery or synthetic voices? Ultimately, these design decisions must be considered in relation to platform architecture and the results of content analysis: how do structural constraints encourage or limit certain choices of content and design, and how do these interactions shape the selection, presentation, and intended effect of historical messages? Does aesthetic presentation support a factual, evidence-based, and critical understanding of the past, or does media design risk subverting—or even replacing—reflection and source-based reasoning?

Civic Responsibility: Analysis of historical content remains incomplete without reflection on ethical and civic responsibilities in digital environments. When engaging with historical content on social media, students might ask themselves: Does the content present the historical topic in an accurate, balanced, and transparent manner? Does it respect democratic principles, inclusivity, and minority perspectives? Does the content encourage critical thinking, or does it rely on simplification, emotionalization, provocation, or even manipulation? Who benefits from the circulation of this content, and who may be harmed or marginalized by it?

A key aspect of civic responsibility concerns how users interact with historical content online. Students should discuss: In the case of an untrustworthy, misleading, or problematic post, could interacting with it—by liking, sharing, or commenting—unintentionally legitimize it or increase its visibility? What responsible alternatives exist, such as reporting inappropriate content, contextualizing it by linking to reliable sources or clarifying which aspects are questionable or disputed, or simply disengaging? When interacting with problematic content, could your comment unintentionally increase its visibility, lend it more legitimacy, contribute to its virality, or expose yourself to reputational or social risks? Reflecting on these questions encourages deliberate, informed, and responsible participation in digital public discourse, ensuring that engagement with historical content is both thoughtful and ethically aware.

Optional Re-Design Task: As a concluding exercise, students can apply their critical insights by redesigning selected content in small groups, focusing on combining historical accuracy and ethical communication with the media logic of user-generated content platforms. They can add supporting evidence and references, incorporate multiple perspectives, revise visuals or language to reduce bias, or adapt formats—such as posters, infographics, or short videos—to engage audiences effectively, all while maintaining high standards. Groups are encouraged to share their redesigned content with the class or submit it for review, reflecting on how their changes enhance historical accuracy, ethical communication, and audience engagement in digital contexts.

5.3 Risk Management in Engaging with Historical Content on Social Media

While social media offers significant opportunities for history education, it also entails risks for students and teachers that require deliberate risk management. The considerations outlined below do not constitute empirically validated best practices; rather, they are informed by classroom experience and professional reflection. Systematic research on effective risk minimization in history education involving social media and AI-generated content is still limited and urgently needed.⁴⁰

⁴⁰ To date, there is no specialized literature for history teachers addressing “risk preparedness” or “risk management” in relation to social media in history education, although surveys indicate that many history teachers are concerned about these issues. See Okumuş, O. (2019). *History teachers’ opinions about the use of*

At the outset of the teaching unit, responsible historical instruction requires that teachers assess students' prior historical knowledge as well as their experiences with the topic in social media environments. Understanding what learners have already encountered, interpreted, or internalized online enables contextualized guidance, helps anticipate misconceptions, and supports historically grounded inquiry. As a guiding principle, unrestricted exposure to social media should be minimized, while curated, curriculum-aligned engagement should be maximized. Given that students often lack sufficient orientational historical knowledge to independently assess online content, all work with social media must be embedded in structured scaffolding and reflective classroom practices.

Risk management in history education should focus on a limited set of core dimensions: historical misinformation and AI-generated content; ideological bias and radicalizing narratives; the permanence of digital traces; and the ethical implications of participating in public historical discourse. Rather than encouraging extensive exploration of unmoderated platforms, these issues should be addressed through guided source analysis and comparative work. Equally important is the development of algorithmic literacy, enabling students to understand how platform logics, engagement metrics, and recommendation systems shape the visibility and interpretation of historical narratives. Ethical reflection should accompany all activities, fostering responsible commenting, sharing, and historical representation.

Risk management also extends to teachers themselves. Professional responsibility, legal considerations, exposure to harmful material, and the need for continuous professional development in digital, AI-related, and historical competencies pose significant challenges. Collaborative exchange, institutional support, and ongoing training are therefore essential. Ultimately, risk management in historical social media education is inseparable from historical skill development. When grounded in students' prior knowledge and experiences, carefully guided engagement with digital media can support historical understanding, critical judgment, and civic responsibility without compromising ethical or professional standards.

5. Concluding Remarks

This essay has shown that engaging with historical content on social media is both inevitable in today's digital landscape and full of potential to enrich history education. Realizing this potential requires two complementary approaches. First, a clearly defined, subject-specific conceptual framework is essential—one that teachers can internalize and convey to students to navigate digital historical content effectively. Such a framework should cultivate structural understanding of platform and media logics, critical engagement with AI-generated content, ethical responsibility online, along with students' historical literacy and judgment.

Advancing empirical research in this area is crucial. While qualitative case studies and best-practice examples provide valuable, context-sensitive insights, they often lack generalizability, are affected by selection bias, focus on short-term outcomes, and leave questions of long-term impact and transferability unresolved. Addressing these gaps requires complementary methods, including controlled comparative studies, longitudinal research, and meta-analyses, to consolidate evidence and inform effective strategies for digital history learning.

Ultimately, this essay underscores that social media can serve as a powerful educational resource when guided by a robust theoretical framework and reflective, research-informed practice. By combining structured pedagogical guidance with rigorous study of digital interventions, history education can harness the opportunities of the digital age to foster historical literacy, critical thinking, and civic engagement among students.

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